

WAYS TO INCREASE FOOD PRODUCTION IN BUKHARA REGION

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Abstract

In this article, the food independence and security programs of the UN Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) and the World Health Organization, the decisions of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan to ensure the food independence and security of our country, their main tasks, the decision on additional measures for comprehensive socio-economic development of Bukhara region in 2022-2026 and further improvement of the population's standard of living, its main parameters, increasing the volume of food production in the region Analytical data, suggestions and recommendations are presented.

Key words

Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), food industry, food industry association, food safety, food independence, integration, clusters, key indicators of retail trade, closed circulation irrigation.

According to the Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations (FAO) and the World Health Organization, more than 840 million people in the world do not have the opportunity to eat enough. This means almost one in eight of the world's population. In addition, more than 30 percent of the planet's population is suffering from malnutrition, the lack of the most basic microelements and vitamins, which clearly shows how urgent the issue of ensuring food safety is.¹⁴⁹

Within the framework of the state program to increase the production and export of food industry products, which is an important sector of the economy of any country and one of the most relevant sectors of the state's life, many issues have been resolved today. In particular, the production of exportable agricultural products is considered a priority based on the demands of the world market. In order to implement this work, the requirements of studying and implementing international standards for the food industry remain an urgent task for entrepreneurs and agro-specialists.

¹⁴⁹ <http://uzbekistan-geneva.ch/oziq-ovqat-xavfsizligini-ta-minlash-ustuvor-vazifa.html>

According to statistics, on average, more than 16 million tons of fruits and vegetables, legumes and legumes, about 1,5 million tons of meat, and about 10 million tons of milk are produced in our country. However, the level of their industrial processing is on average 15-20 percent. This in itself confirms that the agro-logistics system is not well developed in the republic and systematic work should be carried out in this direction. In addition, the lack of storage and sorting services of agricultural products is not at the required level, which leads to the waste of at least 30% of the cultivated crop. The fact that sometimes there are big problems even in conducting laboratory tests of the grown products in accordance with international standards makes a person sad. In short, there are enough problems in the food industry of our republic.

The production of food products according to scientifically proven norms, in addition to the preparation of sufficient level and assortment, as well as compliance with standard standards for the health of the population, which increases the quality of consumer goods, the production of necessary reserves of basic food products and One of the priority tasks of the Union of Food Industry is to develop an advanced industry of food products for storage, provision of regions, to achieve the highest level of food supply to the population, and to develop export potential.¹⁵⁰

The decision of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan was adopted in order to ensure the food independence and safety of our country.

In 2022-2026, in accordance with the decision on additional measures for comprehensive socio-economic development of Bukhara region and further improvement of living standards of the population, the following was determined.

In Bukhara region, in 2022-2026, the volume of gross regional product will increase by 1,4 times, the volume of industrial products by 1,5 times, the production of agricultural products by 1,2 times, the volume of services by 3,1 times, the volume of construction works by 1,5 on the other hand, the parameters of the target indicators in the section of cities and districts, implying an increase, were approved.

A total of 20506 food production enterprises operating in the Republic of Uzbekistan during the months of January-November 2021 made 44804,3 billion. products worth soums were produced.

Compared to January-November 2020, the physical volume index of the network was 105,3%.

¹⁵⁰ <https://ufia.uz/archives/1059>

The highest share in the total volume of products produced by food production enterprises on a national scale is Tashkent city 16,2% (2,891), Samarkand region 12,4% (2114), and Tashkent region 12,1% (2144) corresponded to the contribution.¹⁵¹

The number of enterprises and organizations operating in the field of accommodation and catering services (as of April 1, 2023, in units) As of April 1, 2023, enterprises and organizations in the area of accommodation and catering services number was 2091, which is 86,4% compared to the corresponding period of the previous year. The main factor in the increase in the number of enterprises and organizations in the field of total living and dining services is food and beverage delivery services by 85,2% (the share of the total living and dining services sector is 83,0%). accommodation services accounted for 92,7% (the share of the total accommodation and food services sector was 17,0%).¹⁵²

Integration and clusters are useful in ensuring food security and increasing the volume of exports.¹⁵³

Integration of production, processing, storage, export of products in the field of fruit and vegetables, increasing the volume of exports is important in ensuring food safety.

2021 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan in order to mutually integrate the processes of production, processing, storage, service and sale (export) of products in the field of fruits and vegetables in the republic, to develop the activities of clusters (cooperation), to ensure food safety and to increase the volume of exports The decision of December 15 "On measures to support the fruit and vegetable industry by the state, to further develop the cluster and cooperation system in the network" was adopted.

According to this decision:

- 6-month preferential loan for farmers, peasant farms and other producers of fruits, grapes, vegetables, potatoes, sugar crops, greens and medicinal plants, legumes and oilseeds at an annual rate of 14% (including 2% bank margin) up to 50% of the value of the crop loans are allocated for a period of 12 months;

- 12-month "revolver" loan at the rate of 14% per annum (including 2% bank margin) will be allocated to the processors, storage and exporters of fruits and

¹⁵¹ <https://www.buxstat.uz/uz/matbuot-markazi/buxoro-yangiliklar/6858-o-zbekiston-respublikasida-oziq-ovqat-mahsulotlari-ishlab-chiqarish-sanoati>

¹⁵² file:///C:/Users/user/Downloads/KORXONALAR%20VA%20TASHKILOTLAR%20FAOLIYATINING%20UMUMI Y%20TAVSIFI.pdf

¹⁵³ <https://yuz.uz/uz/news/oziq-ovqat-xavfsizligini-taminlash-va-eksport-hajmini-oshirishda-integratsiya-va-klasterlar-qol-keladi>

vegetables to replenish working capital required for the purchase of cultivated agricultural products. In this case, it is not allowed to extinguish other loans of clusters and cooperatives from commercial banks from the account of this loan.

Table 1.

The main indicators of retail trade in Bukhara region¹⁵⁴

Indicators	2021 y.	2022 y.	Difference in %
Retail turnover, sales in all trade sectors, including catering organizations, bln. Soum	9 246,2	12 188,2	2 942,00
in cities	5 359,1	6 303,2	944,10
in rural areas	14 194,4	13 371,4	-823,00
From the total volume of retail trade turnover, bln. soum:	5 296,8	11 633,9	6 337,10
food products	8 897,6	5 855,9	-3 041,70
non-food items	3 409,5	13 264,4	9 854,90
Retail turnover per capita, thousand soums	491,1	384,3	-106,80
Stocks of goods in retail trade networks (at the end of the year, including consignment goods)	310,1	465,3	155,20
total, billion soums	39,0	43,0	4,00
on days of turnover	11 763,0	12 187,0	424,00
Retail trade facilities (by the end of the year)		-	
total, thousand	119,0	382,0	263,00
per 10,000 inhabitants	1 082,0	1 140,0	58,00
Catering organizations (by the end of the year) in total, thousand	9 246,2	12 188,2	2 942,00

The data of the above table shows that the analysis of the main indicators of retail trade in the case of Bukhara region was as follows.

In 2021, the volume of sales in all trade sectors, including retail turnover, catering organizations, is 9246,2 billion, 12188,2 billion soums in 2022, amounting to 2942,0 billion soums, increased to soum. These indicators will be 5359,1 billion in 2021 in cities, soums, and in 2022 it will be equal to 6303,2 billion soums, and this figure has increased by 944,1 billion soums.

To see that in the rural areas of Bukhara region, in 2021, it is equal to 14194,4 billion soums, and in 2022, it is equal to 13371,4 billion soums, and this indicator has decreased to 823,0 billion soums possible.

In the example of the Bukhara region, the volume of food products in the total volume of retail trade turnover in 2021 is 8897,6 billion soums, and in 2022 it will be

¹⁵⁴ file:///C:/Users/user/Downloads/ISTE'MOL%20BOZORI.pdf

5855,9 billion soums, it can be seen that this figure has decreased to 3041,7 billion soums.

The volume of non-food goods in the total volume of retail trade turnover in 2021 is 3409,5 billion soums, and in 2022 it will be 13264,4 billion soums, and it can be seen that this figure has increased to 9854,9 billion soums.

The volume of retail trade turnover per capita will be 491,1 billion soms in 2021, and 384,3 billion soms in 2022, as a result, it can be seen that this figure has decreased by 106,8 billion soms.

From the data in the above table, it can be determined that as of April 1, 2023, the number of permanent residents of Bukhara region was 2 016 600 people. As a result, due to the increase in the population, the volume of food products in the total volume of retail trade turnover in 2021 will be 8897,6 billion soums, and in 2022 it will be 5855,9 billion soums, and this figure has decreased to 3041,7 billion soums.

Therefore, our province faces the task of solving a number of problems. We would like to give a number of suggestions and recommendations to perform such tasks.

First of all, it is to identify and find ways to meet the daily growing needs of a large number of people for food products.

Secondly, to determine the volume of demand and supply in the market, and to develop ways of specialization to ensure food independence in the regions of the region, depending on the results of marketing research.

Thirdly, due to the fact that our region is located in a desert area, there is a water problem. It would be appropriate if we use foreign experience to prevent the water problem in time. For example, closed circulation irrigation is used in America. Fresh water can be reused several times depending on the type of plant. It is possible to water cotton by adding salt water to 75 percent fresh water, and then water another plant out of it. The main thing is that it will be possible to store water.

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